

Supplementary Materials*Antifungal Susceptibility Testing Panels and MIC Ranges***Sensititre YeastOne® (SYO) broth microdilution (Thermo Fisher Scientific)**

The SYO panel contained predefined concentrations of antifungal agents as follows:

Antifungal agent	Predefined concentrations
Amphotericin B	0.12–8 µg/mL
Anidulafungin	0.015–8 µg/mL
Caspofungin	0.008–8 µg/mL
Micafungin	0.008–8 µg/mL
Fluconazole	0.12–256 µg/mL
Itraconazole	0.015–16 µg/mL
Posaconazole	0.008–8 µg/mL
Voriconazole	0.008–8 µg/mL
5-flucytosine	0.06–64 µg/mL

SYO Method:

Inocula were prepared from 24-hour cultures grown on Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) at 35°C, adjusted to a turbidity equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard. The dried panels were rehydrated with 100 µL of yeast suspension per well using a multichannel pipette, sealed, and incubated at 35°C for 24–48 hours in a non-CO₂ incubator. MIC endpoints were read manually after 24 hours by observing the color change from blue (no growth) to red (growth), with the MIC defined as the lowest antifungal concentration inhibiting visible growth [1].

Etest gradient strip (bioMérieux)

Etest strips employed antifungal concentration gradients as follows:

Antifungal agent	Predefined concentrations
Amphotericin B	0.002–32 µg/mL
Fluconazole	0.016–256 µg/mL
Anidulafungin	0.002–32 µg/mL

Etest Method:

A 0.5 McFarland standard suspension was inoculated onto RPMI 1640 agar supplemented with 2% glucose and buffered to pH 7.0. Etest strips were applied, and plates were incubated at 35°C under moist conditions for 48 hours. MIC values were determined by the intersection of the lower edge of the elliptical inhibition zone with the strip [2].

Quality Control Strains

Each testing day included quality control using *Candida krusei* ATCC 6258 and *Candida parapsilosis* ATCC 22019.

MIC Interpretation

MIC results were interpreted using Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) M27M44S (2022) breakpoints [3]. When CLSI breakpoints were unavailable, European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) breakpoints version 11.0 (2024) were applied [4].

Definitions

MIC₅₀ and **MIC₉₀** were MIC values inhibiting at least 50% and 90% of isolates, respectively [15].

Geometric Mean MICs (MIC_{Geo}) were calculated as the nth root of the product of all MIC values for a given antifungal-species combination [5].

Essential Agreement (EA) is defined as MIC results from the two methods falling within $\pm 1 \log_2$ dilution. EA percentage was calculated as the number of concordant MICs divided by the total tests, with $\geq 90\%$ considered acceptable [6].

Categorical Agreement (CA) refers to the situation when minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) from two testing methods fall within the same interpretive category—such as susceptible, susceptible-dose-dependent (SDD), intermediate, or resistant. The CA percentage is calculated by dividing the number of tests with matching categories by the total number of tests, with a threshold of $\geq 90\%$ considered acceptable [6].

Discrepancies in CA are classified into three types of errors:

Very major errors (VMEs) occur when the reference method (Sensititre YeastOne®) reports resistance, but the test method (Etest) reports susceptibility.

Major errors (MEs) occur when Sensititre YeastOne® reports an isolate as susceptible, but Etest reports it as resistant.

Minor errors (mEs) occur when one method categorizes an isolate as susceptible or resistant, while the other categorizes it as intermediate or SDD. Error rates are expressed as percentages.

An acceptable minor error rate is $\leq 10\%$, and it is important to assess the direction of these errors – that is, whether the AST method tends to overestimate or underestimate MICs compared to the reference broth microdilution (BMD) method. Major and very major errors are generally acceptable at rates below 3% among susceptible and resistant isolates, respectively. Since VMEs represent false susceptibility and carry the highest clinical risk, the FDA requires that fewer than 1.5% of resistant isolates produce VMEs [6].

Supplementary Materials

In summary;

Parameter	Acceptable threshold
Essential agreement (EA)	≥90%
Categorical agreement (CA)	≥90%
Minor errors (mE)	<10%
Major errors (ME)	<3%
Very major errors (VME)	<1.5%

References

1. Thermo Fisher Scientific. Sensititre YeastOne® YO10 Manual. Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc. [Manufacturer's Instruction Manual]. Available from: <https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/SYO>. Accessed [2019 Jan 6].
2. bioMérieux. ETEST® Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing Instruction Manual. bioMérieux. 2012. Available from: <https://health.maryland.gov/laboratories/docs/Etest%20information.pdf> [Accessed 2019 Jan 5].
3. CLSI. 2022. Performance Standards for Antifungal Susceptibility Testing of Yeasts. 3rd ed. CLSI supplement M27M44S. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.
4. The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. 2024. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs for antifungal agents, version 11.0. <http://www.eucast.org/astoffungi/clinicalbreakpointsforantifungals/>
5. Tzar MN, Mustakim S, Yusoff H, Tap RM. 2024. Antifungal susceptibility of molecularly confirmed *Aspergillus* species from clinical samples. *Malays J Pathol* 46(1):71-8.
6. Humphries RM, Ambler J, Mitchell SL, Castanheira M, Dingle T, Hindler JA, Koeth L, Sei K. 2018. CLSI methods development and standardization working group best practices for evaluation of antimicrobial susceptibility tests. *J Clin Microbiol* 56(4):10-128.